

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.2.4.1: Research

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Description

Section 3.2.4.1 assesses the role of the activities, facilities and devices used in Scientific Research as drivers of transportation, introduction, establishment and spread of invasive alien species, including research on alien species for chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control. Scientific education was also considered as an activity related to Research, and therefore, it was included in this section. I conducted a systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This systematic review together with further readings and references suggested by CLAs, internal reviewers (ZOD, FOD and SOD) and external reviewers (FOD and SOD) consisted in the main sources of evidence for this section.

Process overview

I carried out multiple searches in Scopus, read the title and when relevant, also the abstract of the 100 first titles of each search to select the potentially relevant papers. Finding the appropriate searching words was the most challenging aspect, because of the ubiquity of the word "research" in scholar papers.

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms**

TITLE-ABS-

KEY (research OR technolog* OR experiment* AND introduc* OR invasi* OR spread* OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non-indigenous) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI"))

TITLE-ABS-

KEY (research OR technolog* OR experiment* AND invasi* OR spread* OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non-indigenous) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI"))

TITLE-ABS-

KEY (breed* OR technolog* OR engineer* AND introduc* OR invasi* OR spread* OR alien OR exotic OR non-native OR non-indigenous) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 1999 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "AGRI") OR LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA , "ENVI"))

TITLE-ABS-

KEY (accidental OR experimental AND release OR escape AND introduc* OR alien OR invasive* OR invader OR non-native OR non-indigenous) AND DOCTYPE (ar OR re) AND PUBYEAR > 1999

- Search engine

Scopus

- Date

From 24 September to October 2019

- Overview of the search results and selection criteria

Number of search result:

I read the Title and Abstract of the first 100 results of each search ordered by relevance. From these initial searches, I selected and reviewed 7 papers.

Selection criteria:

Selection criteria was that the contribution should address the role of the activities, facilities, gears and devices, used in Scientific Research and Technology (including Science teaching and capacity building) as drivers of transportation, introduction, establishment and spread of invasive alien species. Because of the ubiquity of the word "research" in scholar papers, most of the papers were discarded at this stage. I also included studies where the collection, experimentation, manipulation, rearing or storing of biological organisms for scientific purposes were drivers of transportation, introduction, establishment or spread of these species out of their ranges. However, I excluded all papers related with genomic research, as this will be the focus of another section.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations):

I added 16 additional papers based on experts' knowledge (internal and external reviewers' recommendations), further readings of paper cited and my own expertise.

- Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.)

Number of papers reviewed:

23 (See [Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#))

Fields extracted:

- Publication title
- Year of publication
- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]
- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]
- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]
- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]
- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]
- Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life]
- Comment (free text)

- **Files (code, review templates, etc.):**

[Chapter 3 literature review masterdatabase.xlsx](#)